

Grain yield and other plant characters of a ratoon crop of IR9784-52-2-3-2 as affected by different rates and methods of N placement. IRRI, 1981 dry season (av of 4 replications).^a

Rate and method of placement	Grain (g/plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Field grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	100-grain weight (g)	Nodal tillers (%)	Plant height (cm)	Plant vigor ^b	Grain-straw ratio	Growth duration (days)
30 mg N/kg soil broadcast	9.2 b	18 b	32	24	1.89	74.9	69.9	7 a	1.2	58
30 mg N/kg soil deep placement	10.8 c	19 b	34	18	1.85	76.9	69.2	6 a	1.2	58
50 mg N/kg soil broadcast	16.9 b	25 ab	36	21	1.88	80.5	75.6	2 b	1.2	59
50 mg N/kg soil deep placement	25.1 a	34 a	39	13	1.87	65.7	75.2	1 b	1.0	61
Control	7.6 c	16 b	29	19	1.88	63.9	88.8	8 a	1.0	58
F-test on planned comparison										
Control vs others	**	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	**	ns	ns
Broadcast vs deep placement	**	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level. ^b 1 = extra vigorous; 3 = vigorous, 5 = intermediate or normal vigor, 7 = less vigorous than normal, 9 = very weak and small.

Effect of different sources and levels of nitrogen fertilizers on rice grain yield

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A field experiment was conducted on a loamy sand soil (pH 8.3, organic carbon 0.55%, electrical conductivity 0.05 mmho/cm) in Gurdaspur District of Punjab State to determine optimum nitrogen source and fertilizer rate for irrigated rice. Calcium ammonium nitrate, ammonium chloride, and urea were applied at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha. Each was applied in 3 equal splits: before puddling, and at 21 and 42 days after transplanting. Farming methods recommended for the area were followed and grain yield

Effect of N levels and sources on grain yield of rice variety IR8, Punjab, India.

N (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)			
	Calcium ammonium nitrate	Ammonium chloride	Urea	Mean
60	4.3	4.7	4.8	4.6
120	6.3	7.0	6.9	6.7
180	6.9	7.8	7.3	7.3
Mean	5.9	6.5	6.3	
	No nitrogen = 2.70			
	CD (5%)			
	Level or source = 0.28; level × source = 0.46.			
	Control × treatment = 0.45			

was recorded (see table).

Increasing N level significantly increased grain yield. Ammonium chloride produced maximum yield followed by

urea and calcium ammonium nitrate.

Calcium ammonium nitrate was significantly inferior to ammonium chloride and urea. □

Evaluation of nitrogen availability indices for rice in alluvial soils

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Different methods of testing soil nitrogen levels and their relationship to rice yields in alluvial soils were evaluated in the greenhouse. Five 20-day-old PR106 seedlings grown in a nitrogen-deficient solution culture were transplanted into pots, each with 4.5 kg surface soil (0-15 cm), from 20 Punjab soil sites. Soil pH varied from 7.2 to 10 and electrical conductivity from 0.15 to 2.12 mmho/cm. Treatments of 0 and 100 ppm N as urea

Indices of available nitrogen and their relationship with rice plant parameters.

	O. C. (%)	KMnO ₄ -N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	NO ₃ ⁻ -N	NH ⁺ + NO ₃ ⁻ -N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N ^a
			<i>Available nitrogen (kg/ha)</i>			
Range	0.07-0.78	62.7-207.0	5.4-81.5	3.1-75.3	8.5-156.8	9.4-100.4
Mean	0.44	128.5	25.5	34.5	60.0	46.4
			<i>Correlation coefficients (r value)</i>			
Control grain yield	0.473	0.649	0.132	0.228	0.196	0.515
Percent grain yield	-0.027	0.143	0.159	0.193	0.169	0.004
Control grain uptake	0.433	0.581	0.261	0.288	0.313	0.489
Percent grain uptake	-0.250	-0.100	0.317	0.144	0.263	0.127
Control total uptake	0.476	0.643	0.307	0.300	0.346	0.610
Percent total uptake	-0.050	0.132	0.349	0.190	0.304	0.170

^aAfter 72 hours of soil incubation at 40°C.

and a basal dose of 11 ppm P and 21 ppm K were applied. Grain and straw samples were analyzed for total N.

Soils were tested for available nitrogen by alkaline KMnO_4 -oxidizable N, organic carbon, 2N KCl extractable NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- -N and NH_4^+ -N after incubating the soil in a 1:1 water suspension at 40°C. Correlation coefficients were calculated for yield and N uptake parameters with nitrogen indices (see

table).

Grain yield varied from 3.2 to 19.7 g in control pots, and from 5.3 to 28.3 g in treated pots. Percent grain yield varied from 14.8 to 46.6%, showing 53.4 to 85.2% yield was due to nitrogen application. Total N uptake varied from 9.0 to 44.5 mg/pot and percent N uptake from 11.0 to 48.0%, showing 52.0 to 89.0% uptake was due to applied nitrogen.

KMnO_4 -oxidizable N and NH_4^+

levels after incubation and organic carbon were significantly related to grain yield and N uptake. Grain yield had the highest correlation (0.649) with KMnO_4 -oxidizable N. NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- -N, and $\text{NH}_4^+ + \text{NO}_3^-$ -N did not show significant correlation with grain yield or N uptake. No evaluation methods had a significant relation with percent yield or percent N uptake. □

Management of transplanted rice with seedlings of different ages

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The performance of 25-, 35-, and 45-day-old seedlings was studied at 3 nitrogen levels (0, 60, and 120 kg N/ha) and 15 × 15 and 15 × 10 cm spacing during 1981 wet season. Jaya was planted in the field in a randomized block design in three replications.

Transplanting 25-day-old seedlings produced highest yields, as did increased nitrogen levels. Spacing did not significantly influence yield (Table 1).

Nitrogen level-seedling age interaction (Table 2) indicated that 25-day-old seedlings responded best at 0 and 60 kg N/ha. However, 35-day-old seedlings yielded best at 120 kg N/ha, indicating that yield reductions caused by planting older seedlings may be offset by applying more nitrogen fertilizer.

Table 1. Effect of seedling age, nitrogen level, and spacing on grain yield of Jaya.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Seedling age (days)</i>	
25	5.8
35	5.1
45	4.5
<i>N level (kg/ha)</i>	
0	3.9
60	5.4
120	6.2
<i>Spacing (cm)</i>	
15 × 15	5.1
15 × 10	5.3

TABLE CONTINUED

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Seedling age</i>	
S. Em ±	0.15
CD at 5%	0.31
<i>N levels</i>	
S. Em ±	0.15
CD at 5%	0.31
<i>Spacing</i>	
S. Em ±	0.13
CD at 5%	NS ^a

^aNot significant.

CONTINUED ON NEXT COLUMN

Table 2. Seedling age – nitrogen interaction effect on grain yield.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)		
	25 d	35 d	45 d
0	4.6	3.4	3.6
60	6.0	5.4	4.8
120	6.6	6.4	5.5
S. Em ±	0.26		
CD at 5%	0.54		

Azolla and blue-green algae for wetland rice culture

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Increasing costs of synthetic nitrogen fertilizer are causing biological nitrogen-fixing systems to become more important. The efficiency of using blue-green algae and azolla to provide all or some nitrogen needs of the rice crop was studied during 1981 kharif. Treatments are indicated in the table.

Results show a significant increase in

Effect of azolla and blue-green algae on IR20 rice yield.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	5.2
Azolla incorporated (6 t/ha)	6.2
Azolla inoculated and allowed to grow with rice	5.7
Blue-green algae (10 kg crust/ha)	6.8
25 kg N/ha as urea N + 6 t azolla/ha	6.0
25 kg N/ha as urea N + blue-green algae (10 kg crust/ha)	6.3
CD : P = 0.05	0.60

yield in the treatments where blue-green algae were inoculated at 10 kg crust/ha or when azolla was incorporated (6 t/ha) (see table).

There was no significant difference

between the treatments where azolla was incorporated or BGA applied together with 25 kg N/ha as urea and the corresponding treatments without N fertilizer. □